

Perception of Professors and Undergraduate Students of Engineering at the University of Brasilia (UnB) on Emergency Remote Learning Period in the context of the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Due to the social isolation promoted in Brazil to reduce the number of coronavirus cases (Covid-19), local authorities of Brasilia suspended face-to-face activities. In-person courses of educational institutions were redesigned for the remote format. The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the perception of the Emergency Remote Learning Period (ERLP) from the perspective of undergraduate students and professors of the Civil and Environmental Engineering degrees of the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (ENC) of the University of Brasilia (UnB), through the application of questionnaires and data analysis. The secondary objectives are to identify the teaching methodologies and strategies, the platforms most used by professors, and the courses in the remote format with the highest student approval. A group of undergraduate students from Civil and Environmental Engineering degrees of UnB conducted this research in the course Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams. The research was divided into four steps: technical literature review, data survey, data analysis, and discussion of results. In general, the students consider themselves adapted to the professors' methodologies. The evaluation criteria used are consistent, despite the overload of activities. It was necessary to redesign activities from the professors' perspective, which required effort since many professors had little or no experience with online classes. The most used methodology was direct instruction, also applied in the in-person format; the most used evaluation criteria were assignments, seminars, and class participation; the platform most used in the ERLP is Microsoft Teams, made available by the institution. The results contribute to a critical review of the emergency teaching model in the Covid-19 pandemic in Engineering Education and improve future applications.

Keywords: Emergency Remote Learning Period; Teaching Methodologies; Remote Learning.

1 Introduction

Due to the social isolation promoted in Brazil to reduce the number of coronavirus cases (Covid-19), local authorities of Brasilia suspended face-to-face activities in 2020 (Agência Brasília, 2020). Therefore, educational institutions had to adapt teaching methodologies to the virtual environment.

Remote Learning (RL) for higher education in Brazil stands as a challenge since it is linked to dubious learning quality and low student engagement (Finelli et al., 2018). Veiga et al. (1998) consider that educational institutions should continually rethink and improve their quality of services, evaluation systems, and flexibility, including RL. Many proposals for evaluating RL and ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) applied to RL were made by distinct researchers in the educational context. Key parameters are used to obtain the students' perception of remote classes, for example, access to the internet and the quality of this access, focus level during classes and post-classes studies, engagement in debates, and the adaptability to the methodologies used by the professors (Jesus & Borges, 2014; Silva et al., 2016; Cabanach et al., 2016; Finelli et al., 2018).

It is notorious that RL tends to be more exhausting. Thus, the use of innovative strategies and tools becomes an excellent way to improve learning. The great challenge in RL is constructing a dynamic network that promotes discussion and dissemination of knowledge (Veiga et al., 1998).

In the Emergency Remote Learning Period (ERLP) semester at the University of Brasilia (UnB), professors had to redesign the face-to-face courses for the remote format. As it is a remarkable fact in history, evaluations of

the impacts of this transition on students' and professors' behaviors are essential to maintain the degrees' standards of engineering education (EE) practice. A group of undergraduate students from the Civil and Environmental Engineering degrees of UnB conducted this research in the course Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams.

The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the perception of the ERLP of undergraduate students and professors of the Environmental and Civil Engineering degrees of the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (ENC) of the University of Brasilia (UnB) through the application of questionnaires and data analysis. The secondary objectives are to identify the teaching methodologies and strategies, the platforms most used by the professors, and the courses in the remote format with the highest student approval.

2 Method

The authors divided the research into four steps: technical literature review, data survey, data analysis, and discussion of results.

The consultation of the technical-scientific literature was conducted focusing on RL, active methodologies, and research related to assessing the quality of remote student learning. The platforms used in this step were: Google Scholar, Scielo, publications of the Brazilian Association of Remote Learning (ABED), and papers of scientific conferences. A summary of the review was presented in the Introduction section.

The platform used in the data survey was Google Forms. The questionnaires were directed to two audiences: the undergraduate students (number 1) and the professors (number 2) from the Civil and Environmental Engineering degrees of UnB. The authors defined the questions of both questionnaires according to previous studies from the review step. The main research questions were:

- What is the perception of student performance during ERLP by their perspective and by the professors'?
- Is there an overload of activities for students during ERLP?
- Do the students think that the evaluation criteria of the courses are consistent?
- Are the students adapted to the professors' methodologies during ERLP?
- What are the courses in the remote format with the highest student approval?
- How was the professors' transition from a face-to-face course to a remote environment? Did the course plan in terms of evaluation criteria and content change?
- Do the professors have previous experience in RL?
- Do the students and the professors believe in the possibility of hybrid courses in the future?

Then, the questionnaires were structured to understand the students' and professors' perspectives towards ERLP considering the research questions. The data analysis was conducted in Microsoft Excel, and the results compared to previous studies. Graphs and tables were used to explore the information gathered.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Students' Questionnaire

First, it is necessary to understand the current scenario at UnB in the context of the Emergency Remote Learning Period (ERLP) and Covid-19 pandemic. This teaching modality has numerous differences compared to Remote Learning because there is no extensive pedagogical planning. Most of the time occurs only the adaptation of the content to the online form. The result of a very rapid transition between the methodologies can highly affect students' absorbed content (Minha Biblioteca, 2020).

From the method detailed, 125 answers were obtained from undergraduate students of the Civil and Environmental Engineering degrees of UnB. The results are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1. Answers from Questionnaire 1: Students' Perception of Remote Learning Techniques.

Question	Answers	
(1) Is the number of activities proposed in the courses adequate?	Very Inadequate	7.2%
	Inadequate	40.8%
	Adequate	49.6%
	Very Adequate	2.4%
(2) Are the course assessments consistent with the content administered in the remote format classes?	Little Consistent	8.8%
	Consistent	69.6%
	Very Consistent	21.6%
(3) If you had the option to choose between face-to-face and the remote format, would you take the courses you are enjoying the most in the remote format?	Yes	35.2%
	No	38.4%
	Maybe	26.4%

Figure 1. Answers from Questionnaire 1: Overall Student Performance (A) and Adaptation to Methodology (B).

The overall student performance in the remote courses is presented in Figure 1 (A). The students consider it as average (36.8%), good (50.4%), or even, in some cases, excellent (3.2%). Few participants indicate a bad or terrible performance. By the results presented in Table 1 and in Figure 1 (B), even though the transition was fast, the participants from Civil and Environment Engineering degrees of UnB, in their majority, feel adapted to the methodologies applied by professors (54.4%) and consider their performance at least in at average level. However, the students' perception of good performance may not reflect satisfactory learning quality. ERLP had not been previously tested in these courses. More studies should be carried out in the future with qualitative and quantitative perspectives. Silva et al. (2016) stated that the quality of teaching through the exclusive use of virtual platforms is doubtful and must be constantly evaluated and supervised.

Questions 1 and 2 related to the number of activities and assessments evaluate students' stress conditions. About the number of activities proposed in the courses, 40.8% believe that the amount is inadequate and 7.2% very inadequate, almost half of the responses. This fact is highlighted in the 29 answers to an optional question. The students commented that remote classes are more exhausting than face-to-face, and there was an increase in the workload assigned by each course during the ERLP. Due to the use of assignments and seminars as an evaluation criterion associated with a short deadline.

Despite the comments about the overload of activities, the assessments are consistent to most students (69.6%). This result aligns with students' perception of performance. Less than 10% of the responses consider the assessments little consistent with the classes. In this way, even with the rapid transition to the ERPL, professors successfully made compatible the course program with the problems proposed in assessments.

Moreover, as the teaching format has changed, many students miss the spirited debates about the contents. Surmacz and Lopes (2018) made a study about debates in classes. The authors state that classes with the absence of questions and debates become tiring and without knowledge exchange, being only expository. On the other hand, some students pointed out the advantages of the ERLP since there was no commuting time to the university. Thus, they could dedicate themselves even more to the courses.

About the courses' format, it is noticed a similar distribution among the alternatives presented in Question 3. Even though students classify their performance mostly as good in the ERLP, the face-to-face activities encourage more interactions. Also, there is the possibility of implementing practical workshops as a learning strategy and technical visits, which enriches the students' experience.

Many students in the optional question suggest using hybrid methodologies, with one part of the course as in-person and the other remote. This opinion is aligned with RL principles, in which there are synchronous and asynchronous activities throughout the teaching period with the application of face-to-face tests to evaluate learning (Minha Biblioteca, 2020).

3.2 Professors' Questionnaire

From the application of the method presented, 36 answers were obtained from professors of the Environmental and Civil Engineering degrees of UnB. The results are presented in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2. Answers from Questionnaire 2: Professors' Perception of Remote Teaching Techniques.

Question	Answers	
(1) The course is:	Theoretical	52.8%
	Practical	16.7%
	Theoretical and Practical	30.6%
(2) Do you have any previous experience with RL?	Yes	13.9%
	No	52.8%
	Partially	33.3%
(3) The classes were:	Synchronous	44.4%
	Asynchronous	8.3%
	Both	47.2%
(4) Regarding the activities planned for the students, what level of changes occurred in relation to the face-to-face format? (Scale 1 to 5 - little change to a lot of change).	1	11.1%
	2	19.4%
	3	27.8%
	4	25.0%
	5	16.7%
(5) Regarding the performance of the students in the course in this period you consider that:	Improved a lot	0.0%
	Improved	19.4%
	Remained the same	30.6%
	Worsened	19.4%
	Got much worse	2.8%
	I cannot evaluate yet	27.8%
(6) If you had the option to choose between a face-to-face and a remote format, you would teach this course in either way:	Totally presencial	38.9%
	Totally remote	5.6%
	Hybrid (one part remote and one part face-to-face)	55.6%

The number of courses offered by the department during ERLP was 85. There are professors responsible for more than one course. The answers obtained represent professors responsible for 36 courses, about 42% of the total. According to Question 1 in Table 2, most of the courses are theoretical only, more easily adjusted to the remote format since it does not require laboratory or field sessions. Furthermore, 16.7% are practical only, which are the most challenging courses to adapt to the remote format quickly.

An important observation that should be considered is that more than half of the professors, until the pandemic period, had no RL experience, as shown with Question 2 results. From the 36 responses, 47.2% indicate previous or partial RL experience. A group of professors and students was created to share lessons learned with RL and evaluate the perception of both sides on the ERLP.

As half of the professors did not have previous RL experience, they had to adapt to the new tools to implement their teaching methodology successfully. This adaptation was well seen after the ERLP in Question 6, 55.6% of the professors would like to mix face-to-face classes with remote classes in a hybrid format, and 5.6% would like to make their course entirely virtual. In this way, in-person activities would gain a more practical aspect with less expository content, easily adapted to the remote format in an asynchronous mode.

There were three alternatives about the classes: Synchronous, Asynchronous, or Both (synchronous and asynchronous). In this aspect, it can be observed with Question 3 that only 8.3% of the professors chose to hold only asynchronous classes, which is an outstanding result. It means that 91.7% of the professors are still connected, even virtually, with their students. Veiga et al. (1998) state that synchronous classes are more spontaneous than asynchronous ones. These classes have greater group synergy. Instructors are free to interact with students in an online session by speaking, presenting demonstrations, addressing students via video, and providing quick feedback.

Figure 2. Answers from Questionnaire 2: Teaching Methodologies applied by Professors

Most professors chose to adjust the direct instruction methodology or use it purely in the virtual environment without any modifications. Also, some professors use active teaching (AT) methodologies, such as problem- or project-based learning, gamification, and flipped classroom. AT methodologies are student-centered and contribute to reducing stress, according to Cabanach et al. (2016). It is important to emphasize that the participants use more than one teaching methodology in their classes. Consequently, the number of responses obtained is higher than the number of participants in the survey.

The courses' changes related to planned activities had a uniform distribution in Question 4, with slightly higher grades 3 and 4. Professors had to adapt the activities to the remote format, and this question indicates that this process was different for each course. Especially for the most challenging courses to adapt, those with field

and laboratory sessions, this type of experience was covered with photos, videos, and software simulations. In general, most courses had significant changes.

The same behavior is observed about students' performance from the professors' perspective in Question 5, 30.6% state that remained the same and 19.4% improved or worsened. This evaluation is aligned to the students' perception, as most indicated a good performance in ERLP. Courses with practical activities criterion noted less participation of students in classes, resulting in a worsening of performance. The questionnaires' application occurred in the mid of the ERLP. In some courses, especially with evaluation exams near the end of the period, professors could not notice a change in student performance.

The platform most used in the ERLP was Microsoft Teams, made available by the institution. It is possible to hold synchronous and asynchronous classes and even evaluations through the platform. The professors' second most used platform was Aprender/Aprender 3, which was also made available by UnB. The most used evaluation criteria were assignments, seminars, and class participation, according to the survey.

By analyzing the answers from both questionnaires, we can highlight a few courses with greater acceptance. Most of them are exclusively theoretical and adopt a direct instruction methodology adapted to the virtual context with innovative methodologies. The primary purpose is to make the learning process more collaborative, as discussed in the students' questionnaire results. In these courses, the professors had no previous experience with the remote format. The classes had synchronous sessions and asynchronous content, which substitutes the in-person laboratory practices and field visits.

The courses with the highest student approval, amongst the 85 courses analyzed, use active methodologies, like project-based learning and flipped classes, to motivate students to construct knowledge collaboratively. In these courses, professors' attitude towards this new version of teaching was praised by the students since they offered time for debates in their classes and were accessible to answer questions.

During the first semester of classes in ERLP, there was a significant increase in assessments through assignments, exercises, and projects intended to help students stay focused on their courses. However, when most of the courses opt for a single evaluation criterion that requires more time from the students, the students reported another problem: the overload of activities required in the courses.

As previously presented, students indicated they are more tired during ERLP. Galasso (2014) points out possible reasons for exhausting in RL: the insufficient mastery of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) by both the student and the professor, the inadequate preparation of students for an online course, the difficulties of student interaction with their tutors, colleagues, and technologies, the inefficient management of study time, the excess of activities related to the content of the subjects taught and expectations. These points contribute even more to a high tax of dropout and frustration of students in this learning format and consequently a worse performance.

In courses with lower acceptance among the students, the main complaint was the number of activities proposed and the time committed. In all cases, the professors used three or more evaluation criteria, with tests and numerous assignments. The direct instruction methodology also stood out in these cases since the expository classes were mainly synchronous. In all cases, the professors' perception was that the students' dedication time increased in the ERLP.

4 Conclusions

With the results of the questionnaires and the crossing of responses, this paper was able to bring the results of a survey about the perspective of students and professors regarding the Emergency Remote Learning Period (ERLP) in the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (ENC) at the University of Brasilia (UnB). Professors can observe where the students well accept their methodologies, and in return, the students can see more clearly what is expected by the professors.

In general, the students consider themselves adapted to the professors' methodologies and that the evaluation criteria used are consistent. Moreover, most participants indicate good performance in the ERLP. Meanwhile,

it was also pointed out that the remote classes are more exhausting when compared to the face-to-face model and that there was an overload of activities in specific courses.

From the professors' perspective, it was observed that it was necessary to redesign the activities, which required effort since many professors had no experience with online classes. The most used methodology was the direct instruction method, the same applied in the face-to-face format. Learning evaluation was done mainly through assignments, seminars, and class participation.

The purpose of the research was not to evaluate or qualify the methodologies implemented by the professors. It sought to measure the teaching models' acceptance among the academic community of the Environmental and Civil Engineering degrees of UnB during ERLP. Highlighting methodologies that were better accepted by the students or brought more benefits to the professors. This way, the lessons learned can be implemented in future applications and contribute to EE practice.

5 References

- Agência Brasília (2020). Coronavírus: GDF decreta suspensão de aulas por mais 15 dias. 2020. Retrieved from: <https://agenciabrasilia.df.gov.br/2020/03/14/coronavirus-gdf-decreta-suspensao-de-aulas-por-mais-15-dias/>. Access in April 2021.
- Cabanach, R. G., Souto-Gestal, A., & Franco, V. (2016). Escala de Estresores Acadêmicos para la evaluación de los estresores académicos en estudiantes universitarios. *Science Direct*, v. 7, n. 2, p. 41-50.
- Finelli, L. A. C., Prates, A. E., Soares, W. D., & Sousa, J. de C. (2018). Avaliação da Qualidade da Educação a Distância - EaD na Percepção dos Discentes. *Multifaces*, v. 1, n. 1, p. 28-39.
- Galasso, B. (2014). A Gestão em EaD e seus Múltiplos Aspectos: os Desafios na Implementação de um Curso Online. *ESUD 2014 - XI Brazilian Congress on Distance Higher Education*, Florianópolis, v. 11, p. 679-692.
- Jesus, D. P. de, & Borges, E. M. (2014). A EaD no Contexto Educacional: propostas para avaliação. *Brazilian Association of Remote Learning (ABED)*, v. 13, n. 5, p. 193-209.
- Minha Biblioteca (2020). Conheça as principais diferenças entre educação a distância e ensino remoto emergencial. Retrieved from: <https://minhabiblioteca.com.br/educacao-a-distancia-ensino-remoto-emergencial/#:~:text=A%20pandemia%20do%20coronav%C3%ADrus%20provocou,implementa%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20do%20ensino%20remoto%20emergencial>. Access in April 2021.
- Silva, D., Mendes da Silva, A., Braga Junior, S. S., Lopes, E. L., & Teixeira Veiga, R. (2016). Avaliação da Qualidade Percebida de Cursos Gestão em Nível de Graduação na Modalidade EaD. *Unimep's Management Journal*, v. 14, n. 1, p. 242-268.
- Surmacz, E. C. S., & Lopes, C. S. (2018). A Pedagogia da Pergunta como Estratégia Didática na Aula de Geografia. *Where To!?*, Porto Alegre, RS, Brazil, v. 10, n. 1, p. 99-105, sep. 2018. ISSN 1982-0003.
- Veiga, R. T., Moura, A. I. de, Gonçalves, C. A., & Barbosa, F. V. (1998). O Ensino à Distância pela Internet: Conceito e Proposta de Avaliação. In: Meeting of the National Association of Graduate Studies and Research in Administration, 1998, Foz do Iguaçu, Brazil. *Annals of information management*. Maringá: National Association of Graduate Studies and Research in Administration. Retrieved from: <http://www.anpad.org.br/admin/pdf/enanpad1998-ai-16.pdf>. Access in April 2021.